

The Influence Of Parental Relationship On Students' Educational Attainment At Secondary Level In Karachi, Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 23, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Parent's relation, Educational Attainment, Secondary School, Students, Karachi</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5722503</p>	<p><i>Educators, researchers, teachers, and parents always give top priority to enhance their students' academic achievements. The present study tries to investigate the influence of parental relationships on students' school attainment at secondary level. The data was collected from 130 respondents' students from four schools of Lyari town Karachi. An adopted research instrument Parental Relation (PR) Scale (Parvin, M., 2003), was used to measuring the parents' relations and its impact on students' academic performance at secondary level. Students' last annual examinations, 2017-2018 were measured through obtained results. The quantitative research study design was used to analyze data through correlation coefficient and simple regression. The study findings revealed that secondary student's academic performance was significantly and positively associated with their parents' relations. Results also explained that parents' relations and its different dimensions were significant predictors of the student's academic achievement at secondary level. Moreover, school heads/schools' authorities should develop good coordination relations between school and parents' to helping student's performance during their school activities, and homework. The parent's active collaboration can support a between students' to enhance their academic performance.</i></p>

Introduction

Policy makers, educators, researchers, and teachers are actively engaged to work on different dimensions of students' academic performance and enhance their learning abilities. They tried their level best to making their students unique in all walks of life to prove their talent nationally and internationally to recognize themselves. . In this context, educators, teachers, trainers and researchers have been continuously interested to find out those variables which effectively contributing the academic performance of the students at secondary levels. These variables can be internal or external that impact student's academic performance. These factors may be called students, parents', school, and peer factors, (Crosnoe, Johnson and Elder, 2004). Among these factors' researcher considering the parents factors an attempt has been made to explore the relations and academic performance of students at 9th & 10th the grade at secondary school students of four schools of Lyari town Karachi. In Educational policies of Pakistan has been recognized "Secondary Education" as the third stage of formal schooling. Secondary level education starts at roughly at the age of (12 or 13) and ends up between the age of (15 or 16) years. Although it may be depending on the country and its education system / organization. In this study 9th and 10th grade students have been selected as sample whose age range lie between (13 to 16) years. Respondents obtained result in the annual exam, 2017-18, regarded as their academic achievement where higher result score indicate better academic performance.

Students' academic performance depends upon the parents' attention and their involvement in different academic activities and interest to gain the high quality of learning in the annual examination (Barnard, 2004; Henderson, 1988; Shumox and Lomax, 2001). Study findings have also revealed that the due role, continuous struggle, and parental involvement can bring unexpected results in the child's academic performance, (Fan, 2001, Smit and Slegers, 2005). This work focused on parents' relations, attitude with their children to promoting academic performance, it explores the parents' supervision, love, appreciation, affection-negligence, during their children learning. The study also highlighted parental relations, parents' behavior, and emotions etc. Parent and student relation have long been considered positive impact on students' academic attainments, (Prindle and Resinski, 1989; Van Meter, 1994). A strong parent student relationship can bring students higher academic achievement, lower negligence and students' dropout rates can complete school education (Ziegler, 1987). Many studies have revealed that good and close parent -students' relationships can boost up academic achievement among students at secondary level, (Holloway, 1987 Caldwell, and Rock, 1988). In this regard other researchers have claimed that good parent-students' relations can stimulate both to become an active that

parenting relation positively influence on a student over all personality especially on his/ her academic development at secondary level (Christian, Morrison, and Bryant, 2000).

Many studies have been conducted by developed countries most of them conducted on parents' involvement with students related to education and at home (Bowen and Lee ,2006 and Patrikakou, 2000). Many research studies were conducted on parents and children and how their relationship effects on their academic results at home, school, how this relationship develops their social contacts and over all academic performance, (Izzo ,1999). At home parents engaged their children on different activities reading, writing, and discussing with them on different issues related with school, friends' that can impact positively on their academic performance, (Jeynes, 2003; Sui- Chu and Willms, 1996). The good parental relation brings better academic performance among children, (Nyarko, 2010). Rafiq et al. (2013) The research was conducted on parental relationship and academic performance of students at secondary level in Lahore city. The study comprises on 160 students both boys and girls of 9th class. Students were selected from both public and private secondary schools. The study result shown that parental collaboration had positive and significant impact on children academic performance, Catsambis (2001). It was also revealed that the parental relationship has powerful impact on childrens' personal and academic achievement.

Aktar, Shahrier and Hridoy (2013) a Bangladesh based study was conducted on parental relationship. The results show that, parental relation was found satisfactory predictor to enhance academic performance. Kalhotra (2013) carried out a study to identify those factors who helps students to get high and low academic achievement in school due parent child relationship. The result revealed that those who are high achievers because of their parents' individual attention loved more than those fathers do not give attention, time, and importance at home. In contrast, their mothers love does not impact in both high and low achievers equally. The other factors, e.g., family members, relatives, friends, and school staff, can contribute positively to provide proper guidance and encourage students to improve their quality of learning and enhance the academic performance. The crucial role of social assistance to accomplishment of students' performance cannot be ignored at different levels particularly at school level (Goddard, 2003). Additionally, parents' interactions, the social structure, motivation, and encouragement can increase the success rate in the academic calendar, (Furstenberg and Hughes, 1995). Chohan and Khan (2010) the study indicates that the positive parent's interaction improves the academic attainment of students. Schmitt, (2010) study observes the impact of school on students' academic achievements at (age 03 to 13). Researchers revealed that parents-students' relations directly effect on children's, their class fellows and teachers all equally promote their academic performance. Bhatia (2012) conducted a study on the family relationships with emotional intelligence of 340 secondary students, data was collected by using random sampling method. The study findings showed that healthy family relationships greatly influence on student's emotional intelligence. Kraft and Dougherty (2012) also investigated the effect of teacher-family communication can engage students at 6th and 9th grade the study sample was 120 students at secondary schools. Results explained that frequent teacher-family communication can immediately develop students' interest and engage them to complete their homework improve their behavior and enhance their class participation performance at secondary level.

Mo and Singh (2008) have conducted a study on parent's relationships and collaboration influences on students' school engagement .The data were collected from 7th& 8th grade school students and their family experiences were analyzed through structural equation modeling. The results certified the significance of parent's participation can develop commitment and achievement among middle school students". The study results show that parental involvement at school brings positive change in the academic achievements. The impact of parental involvement on learners' educational attainment at different streams of education. Krashen (2005) concluded a study which revealed that well -educated parents and their children scored higher on their academic tests/ examination than those parents were poorly educated and do not perform well in academic tests/examination. It is crystal clear that Educated parents can motivate well, communicate well to handle the issues while learning to improve their academic achievements to facilitate their students on schoolwork, activities, and daily learning activities at school. how to overcome their learning problems and make them able to participate at school tests (Fantuzzo and Tighe, 2000). Gadsden (2003) claimed that parental active involvement at early stage can brings outstanding achievement in children's learnings outcome. It also positively effects on the child's confidence levels, learning attitude and class participation that promote the overall academic achievements of the students at different levels. Study shows parental relation it is too difficult for children to maintain their academic performance. Teachers should pay individual attention and using their teaching experience to enhance their learning of those students to learn effectively".

The several studies indicates that those parents who are in conflicting nature with their organization, family and friends have failed to maintain their role parental role and do not supporting their children to perform well in

school (Cohen, 1990; Kurdek and Sinclair, 1988 and Campbell and Mandel, 1990). Many studies have reported that children and adolescents claimed that authoritative parenting style of practice have brought better results in school while comparing with those who adopted different types of parenting styles of practice in families, (Darling and Steinberg and Bush, 2004; Spera, 2006). Turner and Heffer (2005) conducted a study on students and family involved more in higher levels of nurturance and encourages autonomy of the learners who were more successful students in their academic achievement. Dubois et al. (1994) study showed that good parent-child relationships and teachers report are truly predicated the students' academic achievement. US based study was conducted on adolescents the age group (10-12) the sample size were (157) young adolescent were seen at home parental collaboration can impact on adolescent academic achievements and adjustment and involvement, Garg et al. (2002) study revealed that parental factors have positive impact on shaping students perception and academic achievements through molding attitude, extra-curricular activities and reading habits school home work to develop the students perceptions in educational aspiration, (Jeynes, 2003, 2008).

Several Studies were conducted on parental relationship in different countries e.g., Parents -interaction with schools have brought good academic achievement, including the grades (Barnard, 2004; Hill, 2001; Marschall, 2006). Tope (2012) study indicated that students at primarily designed curricula, textbooks are written to develop parents' relationship Parents are primarily responsible for preparing students to learn physically, psychologically, emotionally, by spending time with them, developing relation with them to enhance their learning abilities get good academic achievements.

Research Objectives

The study based on following specific objectives:

RO1. To find out how much difference parental relations as the predictor can create in describing students' academic performance at 9th & 10th grade.

RO2. To discover how much disparity on different dimensions of parental relations can create as predictors in describing students' academic performance at 9th & 10th grade.

Rational of the Study

Parents can play pivotal role in their childrens social and emotional development. Sufficiency or insufficiency of healthy and stable socio-emotional atmospheres in family determines children's development of skill and knowledge in academic as well as non-academic pursuits. Family factors like good parental education, healthy parental relationship, good parent-child interactions, parental acceptance-rejection, proper parental supervision, feeling of love, affection, appreciation of parents towards their children etc. These factors also help to stop the dropout rate of children from primary to secondary and higher secondary levels. These factors are useful to save the resources and energy of parents and state. Nevertheless, if these determining factors of a smooth family relation are somehow absent in children's life then it may be assumed that the impact of these factors badly affect the academic performance and school adjustment of children. In the light of these views, the study attempted to explore the influence of parental relationship on students' educational attainment at secondary level in Karachi, Pakistan.

Hypothesis of the study

The study based on following hypothesis which are given as under:

RH1. There is significant difference between parental relationship and students' academic achievements at secondary level.

RH2. There is no significant difference between parental relations and its different dimensions to explain the performance of students at secondary level.

Materials & Method

The study sample has been selected in two phases. The study sample were selected from four schools of Lyari town, Karachi. The study sample was consisting of (130) students who were belongs to secondary level. Purposively students were selected from four secondary schools of Lyari town Karachi. The students age ranged from (14 to 16) years. Respondents were selected from the secondary schools of urban residential backgrounds securing different grades or results at their last annual examination 2017-18. Students' parents were belonging from different professions with varied levels of monthly income. The respondents last annual examination was regarded as their academic performance. Higher academic result of annual examination indicated better academic achievement. The sample distribution of the respondents according to their grade and gender are given below:

Table 1. Sample Distribution of the Respondents According to Gender and Grade

	Male	Female	Total
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9 th Grade	33	33	66
10 th Grade	32	32	64
Total	65	65	N=130

Research Instruments

Two research Instruments used to conduct this study:

1) Personal and Demographic Information Form (PIF): The instrument was based on following variables, Age, Gender, Class, Name of school, Annual Examination last year, Profession, Mother', Family Monthly Income etc.

2. Parental Relation (PR) Scale (Parvin, M. 2003): The parental relation is a new scale, which has been developed in Pakistani perspective. The scale was developed by Parvin, M. (2003). Fifty-two items were included in this scale. This scale is designed to measure four different variables: Affection-Negligence, Supervision, Parental Relationship and Mental Illness/Legal Involvement. The reliability of the parental relation (PR) scale was determined to carry out this scale on 20 normal adult males and females by using split-half method. Reliability of each sub-scale was determined separately and correlation coefficients for affection-negligence were found to have 0.75, for supervision 0.86, for parental relationship 0.87 and mental illness/ legal involvements were 0.78.

Table-2: Sample of Parental Relation (PR) Scale its number of items with distributions

S. N	Scale	No: Items	Distributions of item number
01	Affection-Negligence	13	09 positive & 04 Negative
02	Supervision	13	08 Positive & 05 Negative
03	Parental Relationships	13	06 positive & 07 Negative
04	Mental illness	13	1, Positive & 12, Negative
	Total	52	24, Positive & 28, Negative

Table-2 reveals the status of four scales of parental relation (PR) scale its number of items with distributions. The scale has satisfactory content and criterion validity gathered from reviews concerning the scales psychometric properties. -1 Affection-Negligence scale enjoy 13 items, out of which 09 item are positive and 04 items are negative -2 Supervision scale enjoy 13 items, out of which 09 items are positive and 05 items are negative. -3 Parental Relationships scale enjoy 13 items, out of which 06 items are positive and 07 items are negative. -4 Mental illness scale enjoy 13 items, out of 01 item is positive and 12 items are negative. Therefore, result shows that among 52 items of the scale 24 items are positive, while remaining 28 items are negative.

There were 06 response alternatives of "Never", "Rarely", "Often", "Almost always" and "Always". For positive items, 1, 6, 8, 9,5 are given according to the above response alternatives and for negative items 12, 7,5,4,0 is given according to above response alternatives. Higher score shows better parental relations, and lower score shows poor parental relations. The sum of all items was the total score of an individual scale of parental relations.

Procedure

The data of the current study have been collected from four schools of lyari town, Karachi such as: 1) Kala KotGovt School (43 respondents having the parental profession of College Teachers", Teachers", University employees' " and Govt. Employees"); 2) ChakiWari High School, lyari (35 respondents possessing the parental profession of Electrician, Shopkeeper and Teachers "); 3) Lee Market Higher Secondary School, Lyari (32 respondents possessing the parental profession of fishing, Small business, Govt; Employee" and , Private Teaching"); 4) Begum Nusrat Bhutto High School, Lyari (20 respondents possessing the parental profession of Electricians, Shopkeeper, Teachers and Govt. Employee"). The respondents were students of 9th & 10th grade of above mentioned schools. The researcher personally had individual meeting before meeting researcher got permission from the head of all schools separately. All the necessary information was shared with the respondents before the administration of the report. Students were asked to complete the questioner on volunteer bases. Ethical protocols followed by the researcher and data were only used for present study. Half

hour was given every respondent to complete the questionnaire. On completion of questionnaire, the respondents were appreciating with the token of gift by their active participation in the study.

Results

To examine the collected data, the correlation, coefficients, and regression analyses were used for data interpretations. The results have been shown as under:

Table 3: Shows correlations and coefficients between parental relations and students' Educational attainment at secondary school levels

Variables	Family Relations	Educational Attainment
Family Relations		
Educational Attainment	.331**	

** = $p < 0.02$

Table-3 Showed that if there is a correlation are existed between parental relationships and students' educational attainment at secondary school level ($r = .331$, $p < 0.02$).

Table 4: Indicated correlation Matrix of Educational Attainment and Family Relations Sub-scales of Students at Secondary level

1	2	3	4	5
1. Academic Performance	.241*	.265*	.211*	.395**
2. Affection-Negligence		.518**	.577**	.213*
3. Supervision			.513**	.315**
4. Parental Relation				.492**
5. Mental Illness				

** There is correlation is significant between two level at the 0.01 (2-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at two level 0.04 (2-tailed)

Table-4 Showed that students' academic performance secondary school was significantly positively associated with family relations variables like affection-negligence ($r = .241$, $p < 0.02$), parental supervision ($r = .265$, $p < 0.02$), parental relationship ($r = .211$, $p < 0.04$) and parental mental illness ($r = .395$, $p < 0.02$). Results presented in Table-3 also showed that there existed significant positive correlations between affection-negligence and parental supervision ($r = .518$, $p < 0.02$), parental relationship and affection-negligence ($r = .578$, $p < 0.01$), parental mental illness and affection-negligence ($r = .213$, $p < 0.04$). Significant positive correlations were also found between parental supervision and parental relationship ($r = .513$, $p < 0.02$), parental mental illness and parental supervision ($r = .315$, $p < 0.02$), parental relationship and parental mental illness ($r = .492$, $p < 0.02$).

Table 5: Regression Analyses of Secondary School Students (SSS)' Educational Attainment on their Family Relations its different dimensions

Regression	Predictors	Un Std. Coefficients		Std. Coefficient	β	P
		B	SE			
SSS' Academic Performance on Family Relation1	Constant	2.94	.348	.331	8.43	.000
	Family Relation	.007	.003		3.81	.000
SSS' Academic Performance on Affection-Negligence2	Constant	3.613	.236	.243	15.27	.007
	Affection-Negligence	.018	.007		2.72	
SSS' Academic Performance	Constant	3.467	.261		13.23	.000

on Parental Supervision ³	Parental Supervision	.022	.008	.265	4.00	.004
SSS ^{***} Academic Performance on Parental Relationship ⁴	Constant	3.647	.257	.211	14.22	.000
	Parental Relationship	.016	.007		2.36	.020
SSS ^{***} Academic Performance on Mental Illness ⁵	Constant	2.069	.467	.395	4.43	.000
	Mental Illness	.044	.011		4.67	.000

1. Adjusted $R^2=0.103$, ($F_{1,118}=14.573$, $P<0.01$)
2. Adjusted $R^2=0.049$, ($F_1, 118=7.317$, $P<0.02$)
3. Adjusted $R^2=0.064$, ($F_1, 118=9.018$, $P<0.02$)
4. Adjusted $R^2=0.038$, ($F_1, 118=5.528$, $P<0.04$)
5. Adjusted $R^2=0.151$, ($F_1, 118=21.944$, $P<0.02$)

Table-4 Showed the value of adjusted R2 is parental relation explained 10.1% variance of educational attainment. Moreover, parental relationships were a powerful predictor to construct differences among students' educational achievements at secondary level. Again, the value of adjusted R2 in Table 4 indicated that the predictor variables i.e., affection-negligence explained 0.04.9%, parental supervision explained 06.3%, parental relationship explained .03.6%, mental illness explained 14.0% variances of criterion variable in educational attainment .. Thus, the parental relations were stronger predictors to create variations among secondary school students' academic achievements.

Results and Discussion

The study investigates the influence of parental relationship on students' educational attainment at secondary level in Karachi, Pakistan. The data was conducted from 130 respondents' students conveniently from four schools of lyari town. An adopted questionnaire Parental Relation Scale of Pervin, M. (2003) was used for this purpose. Academic achievement of students was measured in this study through the last annual examination 2017-2018. The interpretation of the results is discussed as under:

The study first hypothesis showed that there is significant difference between parental relationship and students' academic achievements at secondary level. Results indicated at Table-2 reveals the status of four scales of parental relation (PR) scale its number of items with distributions. Results also described in Table-3 showed that the different dimensions of parental relations i.e., parental affection-negligence" parental relationship and involvement" were significantly positively associated with the students' educational attainment at secondary level. So, in this way results supports the first hypothesis of the study. The study findings have supported by several other studies, (Barnard & Kelly, 1990; Rafiq et al., 2013; Nyarko, 2010; Chowa, Masa and Tucker, 2013).

The study second hypothesis showed that parental relations and its different dimensions would be the stronger predictors to explain students' academic performance at secondary school level. From the results, it was observed that the parental relations explained 10.1% variance of standard variable of academic performance. Thus, family relation was a stronger predictor to construct educational attainment of students at secondary level. Again, it is seen from the results that the predictor variable affection-negligence" explained 5.1% difference of standard variable in academic performance". The present study result showed that the predictor variable and parental supervision explained 6.4% variations of standard variable in academic achievement. Thus, parental supervision was a powerful expression to construct a difference in academic performance of secondary school students". Again, another predictor variable parental relationship explained 3.8% difference of ex variable academic performance. Thus, parental relationship seemed to be an important predictor of academic performance.

In the finally the predictor variable parents' mental illness in the study has been explained 15.1% difference of expression in variables among students in the academic performance. Consequently, parents' mental illness was a powerful predictor to construct a difference variation among students' academic performance at secondary school. So that the results of the study have verified the second hypothesis. Moreover, the results of the present study have got similarity with the findings of other researchers works, (Kamble and Adsul, 2012; Catsambis, 2001; Chohan and Khan, 2010; Schmitt and Kleine, 2010; Turner and Heffer, 2005). Agreeing with these findings, the study conducted by Strage and Brandt's (1999) showed the levels of demand at students and parental autonomy supporting that positively and significantly expressed students' academic achievement in the annual examination 2017-20. The students' personal traits e.g., subject contents, confidence level, personality traits before their teachers and class teachers.

Conclusion

The present study results have supported the research gap that parental collaborations, parental participations, and active role positively impact on students' academic achievements. It has been strongly recommended that an insight will develop among parents, students, educators about the importance of parental relations for better academic achievements and school adjustment of children at secondary level. It is also reported that parents should well familiarize about their involvement, understanding, various dimensions of their positive roles on children's academic performance. The due role of school heads / schools' authorities / school administrations should not be ignored. It can develop the good coordination relations between school and parents' to helping students during their school activities, and homework. Parent's active participation can fill the gap between home and school, and it will also promote students' academic achievements at secondary level.

Recommendations

It is also recommended that policy makers, educators, researchers, and teachers should equally contribute to sort out the reasons and issues of parental relations to create positive learning atmosphere for students at secondary level. Parental relations will help children to take proper initiatives through economic and psycho-social supports. Moreover, children's can easily adapt their school environment and excels in academic activities to show their annual achievements. It is also recommended that parents should give due attention and quality time to overcome many issues of students in the course of their learning and educational attainments.

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